

COMPARATIVE ECONOMICS OF CHEMICAL FREE AND INORGANIC JAGGERY IN KOLHAPUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

Jaggery holds deep cultural significance in India, especially in rural agrarian communities. India accounts for 55% of the world's jaggery production, with Maharashtra's Kolhapur district renowned for its GI-tagged Kolhapuri jaggery. The present study analyzed the cost and returns structure of chemical free and inorganic jaggery in Kolhapur district. The primary data for the agricultural year 2024–25 was used. Kolhapur district was purposively selected; from Karveer and Panhala tehsils, three villages each were chosen based on the highest number of chemical-free and inorganic units. Five producers from each village were randomly selected, following a three-stage sampling design. Per unit capital investment was ₹9,52,789 for inorganic and ₹9,83,587 for chemical-free units. Resource use costs were ₹36,23,425 and ₹34,72,976, respectively. Total returns were ₹46,22,782.90 for inorganic and ₹74,31,630.53 for chemical-free production. The B:C ratio was 1.21 for inorganic and 2.02 for chemical-free jaggery. Break-even points were 225.18 qtls (₹9,08,261.27) for inorganic and 53.58 qtls (₹3,65,107.51) for chemical-free units, indicating superior profitability for chemical-free jaggery driven by health-conscious consumer demand.

Keywords: Jaggery production, kolhapuri jaggery, chemical free jaggery, cost return analysis, break even analysis, geographical indication, net return.

Introduction

Jaggery, or "gur," is a traditional, unrefined sweetener made from sugarcane, widely consumed in India for its nutritional, cultural, and medicinal significance. Globally, about 13 million tonnes of jaggery are produced annually, with India contributing roughly 55%, followed by Colombia at 11%. Major producing states include Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, and Gujarat, with Kolhapur district renowned for its GI-tagged jaggery. In 2023–24, India harvested approximately 4,531.6 lakh metric tonnes of sugarcane, of which 450–650 lakh tonnes were diverted for jaggery production, yielding an estimated 6–7 million tonnes. The sector provides employment to over 2.5 crore people and per capita consumption is about 4–5 kg/year. Jaggery is nutritionally superior to refined sugar, containing over 70% sucrose, essential minerals such as calcium (40–100 mg), magnesium (70–90 mg), potassium (10–56 mg), iron (10–13 mg), and vitamins including A, B, C, D2, and E. This study examines the comparative

economics of chemical-free and inorganic jaggery in Kolhapur district, evaluating costs and returns structure and profitability.

Material And Methods

Kolhapur district was purposively selected due to its renowned jaggery production, supported by favourable agro-climatic conditions for high-yield sugarcane cultivation. Karveer and Panhala tehsils, having the highest number of jaggery processing units, were chosen. From these, 60 jaggery producers, 30 chemical-free and 30 inorganic, from six villages were selected using three-stage sampling. Primary data for 2024–25 on production, inputs, costs, and returns were collected through personal interviews. Analysis included tabular comparison of fixed cost, variable cost, gross return, net return, and benefit–cost ratio, along with break-even analysis and multiple regression to identify significant production factors.

Results And Discussion**Capital Investment in Establishment of Jaggery Processing Unit****Table 1 :Capital Investment in Establishment of Jaggery Processing Unit**

Sr.no	Items	Inorganic jaggery		Chemical free jaggery	
		Units	value (Rs.)	Units	value (Rs.)
1	Land	0.207	695000 (72.94)	0.212	711468 (72.33)
2	Shade	1	93333 (9.79)	1	94633 (9.62)
3	Vafa	1	17600 (1.84)	1	18413 (1.87)
5	Generator	1	40200 (4.21)	1	38233 (3.88)
6	Electric Motor	1	20867 (2.19)	1	21450 (2.18)
7	Juice Storage Tank	1	5232 (0.54)	1	6177 (0.62)
8	Filter Plates	2.4	471.66 (0.04)	2.5	495.33 (0.05)
9	Iron Scrapper	2.8	1766.66 (0.18)	2.76	1671.67 (0.16)
10	Mould		3198.33 (0.33)		3616.67 (0.36)
11	Kahili(pan)	1	32933	1	44367

			(3.45)		(4.5)
12	Plastic Pipe	1	580 (0.06)	1	572 (0.05)
13	Zarya(skimmer)	3.033	1032.33 (0.1)	2.833	1028 (0.1)
14	Water Tank	1	1000 (0.1)	1	1144.33 (0.1)
15	Furnace	1	39100 (4.1)	1	39800 (4)
17	Spade	4.4	474.5 (0.04)	4.8	517.63 (0.05)
	Total		9,52,789 (100)		9,83,587 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis show percentage to total)

The investment made for the establishment of jaggery processing units included investment on infrastructure, machinery and equipments. Table 1 represents the capital investment in establishment of jaggery processing unit. The investment in land forms the largest share of the total capital cost in both types of jaggery units. In the case of inorganic jaggery, the land cost is ₹695000, which accounts for 72.94 per cent of the total investment. For the chemical-free jaggery unit, the land cost slightly increases to ₹711468, making up 72.33 per cent of the total. The shade comes next, with an investment of ₹93333 (9.79 per cent) for the inorganic unit and ₹94633 (9.62 per cent) for the chemical-free unit. The Kahili (boiling pan) costs ₹32933 (3.45 per cent) for inorganic jaggery and increases to ₹44367 (4.5 per cent) in the chemical-free unit. The

higher cost of Kahili in chemical-free jaggery production is due to the use of stainless steel Kahili instead of the conventional iron one. The mould used for shaping jaggery costs ₹3198.33 (0.33 per cent) in the inorganic unit and ₹3616.67 (0.36 per cent) in the chemical-free unit. The higher cost of moulds in chemical-free jaggery production is due to the use of silicone moulds.

The total capital investment required for the inorganic jaggery unit is ₹952789, whereas the chemical-free jaggery unit requires near about same, but slightly higher investment of ₹983587, mainly due to the use of upgraded, food-safe, and process-specific equipment suited for chemical-free production

Resource Use and Cost Incurred in Jaggery Production.

Table 2: Average Category wise Resource Use and Cost Incurred on Jaggery Processing Unit

Sr.No	Particulars	Inorganic Jaggery		Chemical Free Jaggery	
		Qty.	Value (Rs)	Qty.	Value (Rs.)
A	Raw Material				
1	Sugarcane Used (Tonnes)	975.1	2861967 (78.98)	965.8	2821681.28 (81.04)
B	Labour Cost(man Days)				
1	Sugarcane Cutting(man Days)	731.32	213018.75 (5.87)	724.35	217305 (6.32)
2	Transportation		7520 (0.2)		7236.67 (0.21)
3	Crushing(man Days)	487.55	146265 (4.03)	482.9	144870 (4.21)
4	Gulvi(man Days)	130.37	65183.33 (1.79)	129.7	64850 (1.88)
5	Adkari(man Days)	356.4	106920 (2.95)	353.9	106170 (3.09)
6	Helper(man Days)	167.67	50300 (1.38)	173.67	52100 (1.51)
	Total(man Days)	1873.31	589207.08 (16.26)	1864.52	592531.67 (17.24)
C	Chemicals				
1	Hydrous Powder(kg)	309.83	62753 (1.73)	-	-
2	Phosphoric Acid(kg)	220.17	39257 (1.08)	-	-
3	Artificial Colours (Kg)	22.92	12201 (0.33)	-	-
	Total	552.92	114210 (3.15)	-	-
D	Clarifying Agents				
1	Lime(kg)	261.33	9281	215.28	7892.42

			(0.25)		(0.22)
2	Bhendi Powder(kg)	-	-	13.7	4453.04 (0.12)
	Total	261.33	9281 (0.25)	228.98	12345.46 (0.35)
	Total Chemical and Clarifying Agents (C+d)	814.24	123492	228.98	12345.46
			(3.4)		(0.35)
E	Fuel and Electricity				
1	Fuel (tonne)	1.56	1113 (0.03)	1.42	1022.4 (0.02)
2	Electricity		43880 (1.21)		41796 (1.21)
	Total		44993 (1.24)		42818.4 (1.24)
F	Khadi Cloths		3766.67 (0.1)		3600 (0.1)
	Grand Total		3623425 (100)		3472976.8 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis show percentage to total)

The total working capital for the inorganic jaggery unit amounts to ₹3623425, while the chemical-free jaggery unit requires a lower investment of ₹3472976.80. The major cost component in both units is sugarcane, with the inorganic unit using 975.1 tonnes costing ₹2861967 (78.98 per cent) and the chemical-free unit using 965.8 tonnes Sugarcane costing ₹2821681.28 (81.04 per cent). Labour cost is a crucial component in jaggery production. Labour costs are slightly higher in the chemical-free jaggery unit at ₹592531.67 (17.24 per cent) with 1864.52 man-days. Compared to ₹589207.08 (16.26 per cent) with 1873.31 man-days in the inorganic jaggery unit, owing to more careful handling and greater reliance on manual processes.

A major cost difference arises in the use of chemicals ₹114210 (3.15 per cent) in inorganic jaggery is spent on hydrous powder, phosphoric acid,

and artificial colours, which are completely eliminated in chemical-free jaggery. Instead, the chemical-free unit uses natural clarifiers like bhendi powder along with lime, totalling only ₹12345.46 (0.35 per cent) compared to ₹123492 (3.40 per cent) for chemical and clarifying agents in the inorganic unit. Fuel and electricity costs are nearly identical in both models, with ₹44993 (1.24 per cent) in inorganic and ₹42818.40 (1.24 per cent) in chemical-free.

Overall, the chemical-free unit demonstrates cost efficiency mainly by eliminating chemicals and using natural alternatives, resulting in a lower total working capital despite slightly higher labour inputs.

Cost and Returns from Jaggery Production**Table 3: Category wise per season pattern of cost and returns from jaggery unit**

Sr.no	Particulars	Inorganic jaggery		Chemical free jaggery	
		Qty	value (Rs)	Qty	value (Rs.)
TOTAL COSTS					
1	Land Rent		24325 (0.63)		24901.38 (0.67)
2	Depreciation		25469.32 (0.66)		26614.9 (0.72)
3	Interest on fixed capital (@10 %)		25778.9 (0.67)		27211.9 (0.74)
4	Interest on working capital (@10 %)		120780.83 (3.16)		115765.89 (3.15)
	Total fixed cost		196354.05 (5.14)		194494.07 (5.30)
4	sugarcane (Tonnes)	975.1	2861967 (74.92)	965.8	2821681.28 (76.93)
5	Total chemical and clarifying agents (Kg)	814.24	123492 (3.23)	228.98	12345.46 (0.33)
6	Total labour (man days)	1873.3	589207.08 (15.42)	1864.51	592531.66 (16.15)
7	fuel and electricity charges		44993 (1.17)		42818.4 (1.16)
8	khadi cloths		3766.66 (0.09)		3600 (0.09)
	Total variable cost		3623425 (94.85)		3472976.8 (94.69)
	Total cost		3819779.1 (100)		3667470.41 (100)

TOTAL RETURNS

1	Jaggery produced(tonnes)	114.61	4622782.9	109.06	7431630.53
2	Net returns		948108.88		3942441
3	B:C Ratio		1:1.21		1:2.02
4	Per Qtl cost of jaggery	1 Qtl	4033.49	1 Qtl	6814.25
5	Recovery (%)		11.65		11.29

(Figures in parenthesis show percentage to total)

The total cost of production for inorganic jaggery is ₹3819779.10, while for chemical-free jaggery it is slightly lower at ₹3667470.41. Total fixed cost was found to be ₹196354.05 in case of inorganic jaggery while ₹194494.07 in case of chemical free jaggery. The total variable cost amounts to ₹3623425 for inorganic jaggery and ₹3472976.80 for chemical-free jaggery. In terms of returns, chemical-free jaggery generates significantly higher income of ₹7431630.53 from 109.06 tonnes produced, whereas inorganic jaggery yields ₹4622782.90 from 114.61 tonnes. Net returns stand at ₹948108.88 for inorganic and

₹3942441 for chemical-free jaggery, resulting in a B:C ratio of 1.21:1 for inorganic and 2.02:1 for chemical-free, indicating much higher profitability in the latter. The per quintal price of jaggery is ₹4033.49 in case of inorganic and ₹6814.25 in case of chemical-free jaggery. Chemical-free jaggery earns much higher returns due to its high price per unit and market demand. This is due to its health benefits, natural taste and absence of harmful chemicals.

Break-Even Analysis**Table 5: Break-Even Analysis**

Sr.No.	Particulars	Inorganic Jaggery	Chemical free jaggery
1	BEP in Physical terms(Qtl)	225.18	53.58
2	BEP in Monetary terms (Rs)	908261.27	365107.51
3	Actual Production (Qtl)	1146.1	1090.6
4	Margin of safety (Qtl)	920.92	1037.02
5	Margin of Safety (%)	80.35	95.08

The break even point for inorganic jaggery was 225.18 qtls while for chemical free jaggery it was 53.58 qtls in physical terms. In monetary terms, It was found Rs.908261 and Rs.365107.51 for inorganic and chemical free unit respectively. The margin of safety for inorganic jaggery was 80.35 % and 95.08 % for chemical free jaggery. The low

break even point and high margin of safety this shows that chemical free jaggery is highly profitable business than inorganic jaggery.

Distribution of Total Chemical Free Jaggery Produced in Different Forms

Table shows the distribution of jaggery produced by the selected producers in different forms such as slab, cube, and powder.

Table 6: Distribution of Total Chemical free jaggery produced in different forms

Particulars (Forms of jaggery)	Qty (Tonnes)	Value (Rs)
Jaggery slab	32.71 (29.99)	1439240 (19.36)
Cubes	54.53 (50.02)	4092477 (55.06)
Powder	21.81 (19.99)	1899914 (25.56)
Total	109.06	7431630

(Figures in parenthesis show percentage to total)

A total of 109.06 tonnes of chemical-free jaggery worth ₹74,31,630 was produced, distributed across cubes, slabs, and powder. Jaggery cubes formed the largest share with 54.53 tonnes (50.02%) valued at ₹40,92,477 (55.06%). Their dominance is mainly because of uniform shape, convenient packaging, and higher consumer preference. Jaggery slabs contributed 32.71 tonnes (29.99%) valued at ₹14,39,240 (19.36%). Although slabs still hold importance in traditional and bulk consumption, their lower value share is due to non-standardized form, storage difficulty, and relatively lower market demand. Jaggery powder, at 21.81 tonnes (19.99%) with a value of ₹18,99,914 (25.56%), shows high value

addition despite its smaller share in quantity, as it suits modern consumer needs, health-focused products, and ready-to-use applications.

Statistical Analysis.

In the regression analysis, raw material cost was found to be statistically significant for both types of jaggery, with a significance level of 1 per cent for inorganic jaggery and 10 per cent for chemical-free jaggery, indicating a strong and moderate influence respectively. Transportation cost was not significant in either case, suggesting it does not have a notable impact on total returns. Labour cost showed a highly significant effect at the 1 per cent level for both types, highlighting its crucial role in the production process.

Table 7 :Results of Multiple Regression Analysis

Sr.No	Particulars		Inorganic Jaggery	Chemical Free Jaggery
1	Raw Material Cost	X ₁	59.96*** (23.033)	0.52* (0.2879)
2	Transportation Cost	X ₂	6880.94 ^{NS} (7471.45)	-33.04 ^{NS} (78.35)
3	Labour Cost	X ₃	485.40***	11.34***

			(104.91)	(1.59)
4	Chemical Cost	X ₄	1593.46 (1292.35)	-196.06*** (60.87)
5	Intercept	a	220709.56	131213.07
6	Coefficient of Multiple Determination	R ²	0.83	0.89
7	F Value		32.14	53.43
8	Number Of Observation		30	30
9	D.F.		29	29

Chemical cost was not significant for inorganic jaggery, while it was highly negatively significant at the 1 per cent level with a negative coefficient in chemical-free jaggery, indicating that an decrease in such cost components is associated with a increase in total return .It was due to lesser the chemical used,higher the price will get for chemical free jaggery increasing total return.

Conclusion

The price of Chemical free jaggery was more and less cost of production resulted into better B:C ratio which is 2.02, than inorganic jaggery 1.21 production indicating that chemical free jaggery production was more profitable.

Regression results showed that raw material and labour costs significantly affect returns for both jaggery types, while chemical cost had a strong negative impact on returns for chemical-free jaggery, as lower chemical use leads to higher prices and better returns.

Chemical free jaggery requires a much lower break-even output and investment than inorganic jaggery while enjoying a significantly higher margin of safety, ensuring better returns and financial stability.

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